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1. Introduction

This deliverable represents the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the EIRENE PPP project. This DMP is strictly designed for the EIRENE PPP project reflecting the activities and nature of the action. Since the project is a coordination and support action (CSA) and not a research action per se, only limited data will be collected or used as part of the project pilot. A separate, robust DMP will be created within the project as part of the development of the EIRENE RI. Nonetheless, the PPP project DMP is a living document that will be updated as needed.

EIRENE RI (Research Infrastructure for Environmental Exposure assessment in Europe) project prioritized in the 2021 Update of the ESFRI Roadmap fills the gap in the European infrastructural landscape and pioneers the first EU infrastructure on human exposome (environmental determinants of health). EIRENE PPP aims to prepare the implementation of EIRENE RI as a consolidated European research infrastructure enabling the development of advanced technologies and complementary services on the characterization of complex environmental exposures and their impact on the European population. This will promote European excellence in Environmental & Health research by providing European researchers with transnational and/or virtual access to harmonised capacities, unique services, and comprehensive data addressing the current and future needs of public authorities.

2. Purpose of the document

The purpose of this Data Management Plan is to appropriately describe the datasets produced within the EIRENE PPP project and the policies and approaches for managing them. As mentioned previously, EIRENE PPP is a Coordination and Support Action and thus does not finance research activities but rather the development of the EIRENE RI.

In this context, the deliverable – Data Management Plan - describes the data management procedures, rules, and policies for the data that will be collected, processed and/or generated during the project and by project partners. This plan has been prepared based on the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan template, Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon Europe, and the GDPR. The consortium will comply with the requirements of Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals regarding the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

3. Data Summary

EIRENE PPP aims to prepare a consolidated European research infrastructure enabling the development of advanced technologies and complementary services on the characterization of complex environmental exposures and their impact on the European population. The goal of the project is to promote European excellence in Environmental & Health research by providing European researchers with transnational and/or virtual access to harmonised capacities, unique services, and comprehensive data addressing the current and future needs of public authorities.

EIRENE PPP project is a CSA concerned exclusively with developing the EIRENE RI framework and thus will only generate a limited amount of data. Apart from the EIRENE PPP Data

Management Plan, an extensive Data Management Plan (DMP) developed in WP3 will describe the entire life cycle of EIRENE RI data.

3.1. Purpose of data collection and generation

The EIRENE PPP project will provide the EIRENE RI consortium with the necessary financial support to complete the Preparatory Phase and prepare the RI for Implementation which is the overall objective of the project. EIRENE PPP will help to tackle key legal, governance, financial, strategic, and technical aspects of establishing a new RI in the European landscape of research infrastructures and obtaining the political and financial commitment of the relevant Member States, Associate and Third countries to guarantee its sustainability.

Therefore, this DMP covers the data and datasets, which are generated within the activities, specifically the Work Packages (WPs) of the project. The datasets, given the composition of the WPs and the character of the project, will comprise of following main categories – managerial data, scientific publications datasets, education and training datasets, communication and dissemination datasets and the deliverables datasets.

Since the other type of data may occur, the DMP will be the living document and the update or upgrade of the document may be necessary.

3.2. Types and formats of the data

Table 1 illustrates the type of data to be collected, processed or created in above mentioned areas of the project implementation. It provides the description of the data, its reference to the type of activity and the description of the purpose of the data/dataset collection.

Table 1 Types and formats of data

Description and purpose	Type	Forms, examples	Formats (includes but not limited to)
Managerial data	Data relevant to management, governance, administration and operation of the Centre of Excellence, also to the implementation of the project – in order to set up effective processes and effective operation of the project.	Governing documents, policies, guidelines, directives, methodologies, rules of operation, administrative documents, meeting minutes, custom data from proprietary SWs.	PPTX, PDF, TXT, RTF, DOC, DOCX, XLSX, CSV, HTML Custom data
Scientific publications datasets	Data generated within the project realization by the project partners to prepare scientific publications, posters and other scientific outcomes, including the presentations etc.	Literature reviews, workshops/training/conferences presentations, surveys and interviews, meeting minutes/notes, scientific publications, scientific data	PPTX, PDF, TXT, RTF, DOC, DOCX, XLSX, CSV, XML, JPG, TIFF, PNG MP4, MOV, WMV CEL, CDF, fasta, fastq, CSV, TSV, NEWICK, HMM, IDAT, XML, SDF, RAW, D, MZML, MSP, BATCHBIN, SKY,
Education and training	Data and materials generated in terms of training and educational activities, including mobilities, internships etc. It may cover also the exchanged know-how.	Presentations, tutorials, numerical data, images, videos, surveys, scientific publications, meeting minutes, meeting notes etc.	PPTX, PDF, TXT, RTF, DOC, DOCX, XLSX, CSV, XML, JPG, TIFF, PNG MP4, MOV, WMV CEL, CDF, fasta, fastq, CSV, TSV, NEWICK, HMM, IDAT, XML, SDF, RAW, D, MZML, MSP, BATCHBIN, SKY,
Communication and dissemination	Data and texts used for the communication and dissemination purposes of the project, data about the project, data about the project and project event's participants.	Marketing, communication and PR materials, materials relevant for events, presentations, press releases, social media releases, media releases, visual material, video recordings, recordings (sound) – interviews, podcasts, publications, the Visual style of the project.	DOCX, DOC, PDF PPTX, PDF, XLSX, TXT, RTF, JPG, TIFF, PNG, MP4, MOV, WMV, HTML, web pages
Deliverables and project documents	Materials and data generated through the project realization and implementation, such as the project deliverables (documents) and underlying data (incl. financial). The data necessary to manage the project, ensure compliance etc.	Documents, presentations, meeting notes, meeting minutes, Questionnaires, photos, videos, contacts.	DOCX, DOC, PDF PPTX, PDF, XLSX, CSV, XML, JPG, TIFF, PNG MP4, MOV, WMV

Formats very much depend on the specific types of data and will be determined later as the project evolves.

Below we provide the basic classification of data:

- Raw data – data used in general as input data for research or other activities. These data may originate from also from public or private resources, data repositories, portals, and databases or may be generated by project partners or will be gathered during the project activities (educational, training, networking etc.)
- Processed data – data that was gathered from the raw data being the input for it. The processed data are usually the outcome of the algorithm on the raw data.
- Generated data – the data originating from raw or processed data. The generated data are gathered by applying models, sets, sequences of algorithms, etc. The data are usually used when elaborating the deliverables and project outcomes, including the managerial data and decision models.
- Personal data – according to GDPR's Article 4, 'Personal data' means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person. From the project point of view, this data may be gathered at workshops, conferences, training, events, recruitments, interviews etc.
- Publications – refer to various forms of published research outcomes such as peer-reviewed research articles in scientific journals, books, chapters in other papers, conference proceedings, technical reports, public deliverables, strategies, plans, policies, white papers, policy papers, positions papers, press releases, texts for communication and dissemination, and other kinds of promotional materials.

3.3. Data origin and utility

The data will originate especially from work packages, activities, and tasks of the EIRENE PPP project, according to DoA. Existing data, including the data from project partners, will be utilized for training purposes, as well as for the preparation of scientific publications.

EIRENE PPP project data will be available for project partners, their staff, researchers, and scientists, but also for secondary use by stakeholders at local, national, and international levels and intergovernmental authorities whenever possible.

3.4. Data sharing and storage

Project data, specifically project-specific documents, will be available for all the project partners on the access-restricted project SharePoint site. Personal data will be treated similarly. Should there be any confidentiality issue, the Data Specialist, Open Access manager, and the Data Protection Office will be contacted. Data, which is expected to be open to the public, will be published on the website or via other specific channels, including the CORDIS and other official publication channels or repositories. The data-sharing policy and logic follow:

1. All the documents the consortium perceives as confidential, including deliverables, which are confidential in the DoA will be shared only internally. This will ensure that only the consortium members can access those specific materials.
2. Project documents, which are perceived as public, will be accessible through the EIRENE RI website.
3. Project deliverables, which are marked as public, will be available through the EC CORDIS website.
4. The presentations (documents, ppt, videos from presentation), which will be marked as public, will be uploaded on the website or to specific sites – e.g., YouTube, where these materials will be publicly shared.
5. Presentations that will be marked as private (e.g., the presentation of unpublished data or when the presenter will not provide consent) will be shared only internally within the internal system and internal channels.
6. Communication and dissemination materials, namely the published articles, press releases, and other outcomes, will be published on the website and on the other websites (e.g., the e-newspapers, and social media).
7. Educational and training documents, which will be open to the public, will be shared on the website. The materials, which will be closed and available only for a specific target group, will be shared only with this specific target group (e.g. the class, students of specific lecture)
8. Administrative documents of internal character will be perceived as confidential and will be stored internally. This personal data will be treated accordingly and available only to relevant staff.
9. The governance documents, policies, directives, and other internal documents will be stored and available internally.
The consortium will promote Open Access in all relevant areas, including the OA, to publications, research data, and also to Research Infrastructures.

4 FAIR data

The DMP follows the “FAIR” data principles, thereby ensuring that the data collected in the project is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. To incorporate the “FAIR” principles, the Data Management Plan considers:

- What data will be generated and/or generated, and processed
- How data are handled
- Which methodologies and standards will be applied and implemented
- Which data will be shared or made open access, and how
- How data will be curated and preserved.

EIRENE PPP endorses the EC’s motto: “to make the data as open as possible, but as close as necessary”. The privacy of the participants involved and the confidentiality of specific results or valuable operational and business knowledge will be protected. In these cases, the data

collected, processed or produced by the project will not be made available for public use. In all other cases, the data will be made available as broadly as possible.

4.1 Making data findable

All data and documents produced by the project and flagged as confidential will only be findable by consortium members and EC internally. Files stored internally should be described by the following naming structure:

filename_version_uploaddate

and project deliverables:

deliverablenumber_deliverableshortname_version_uploaddate.

All public documents and project deliverables will be put on the EIRENE RI website and made easily findable.

Scientific publications will be assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). DOI is a unique alphanumeric string assigned by a registration agency (the International DOI Foundation) to identify content and provide a persistent link to its location on the Internet. The publisher assigns a DOI when an article is published and made available electronically.

4.2 Making data accessible

Confidential project data will be stored internally on the project SharePoint site and open data will be accessible via the project webpage according to the open access policy. The basic information on deliverables and their character are provided in the GA. In general, internal documents will be considered confidential and will be available to project partners. Whenever feasible, EIRENE PPP will publish its results in the form of publications in Open Access (OA).

The project follows the Gold OA principles, as mandated by Horizon Europe.

All project activities aim to align with the European priority of Horizon Europe for Open Access to scientific data and results that are obtained using public funding. The project is aware that data and especially "open data," is at the core of future advances in knowledge, the economy, and society and should be made freely available for reuse by everyone. This will help to increase the visibility of the achievements and to stimulate cross-domain collaboration, which are key elements for the successful fulfillment of future project goals.

4.3 Making data interoperable and reusable

The collected and generated data will adhere to the standard, widely used, and recognizable formats, such as various text formats, PDF, Microsoft Office file formats, MP3, image formats, etc. Using these formats enables the reuse and interoperability of data.

The data produced by the project will also be useful for other Big Data-related policies, projects, and initiatives both at national and EU levels, such as the Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialization.

5 Data security and confidentiality

The EIRENE PPP consortium believes firmly in the concepts of open science and the large potential benefits the European innovation and economy can draw from allowing the reusing of data at a larger scale. Therefore, all data produced by the project may be published with open access – this objective will obviously need to be balanced with the other principles described below.

Personal data (i.e., any information related to an identified or identifiable natural person, such as name, address, and email) is collected and processed in the project. Project partners are responsible for handling personal data exchange between the stakeholders and the project. All project partners are obliged to keep personal data closed unless informed consent is given. Personal data will only be made publicly available once a declaration of informed consent has been signed by the relevant stakeholder and suitable aggregation and/or anonymization techniques have been applied.

All files stored internally on the SharePoint site will only be accessible to the consortium partners and protected by an authentication mechanism. These files will be stored on a cloud service and backed up regularly. Unauthorized users will not have access to these files or to the file structure.

Furthermore, all Project deliverables will be available on the Horizon Europe Participant Portal of the European Commission and this will ensure the long-term preservation and recoverability of the deliverable reports.

Some partners may have Intellectual Property Rights on their technologies and data. Consequently, the consortium will protect that data and crosscheck with the concerned partners before data publication.

A holistic approach will be followed. It will consist methodical assessment of security risks and an analysis of their impacts. This analysis will be performed on the personal information and data processed by the proposed system, their flows, and any risk associated with their processing.

Security measures will include secure protocols (HTTPS and SSL), and login procedures. The data protection and privacy of personal information will include protective measures against infiltration and physical protection of core parts of the systems and access control measures.

6 Legal Aspects

Because the EIRENE PPP project consortium follows the general principle of Open Science approach proposed by the European Commission, i.e., ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary, data handling adheres to the following rules:

1. If there are no legal restrictions or commercialization potential for a dataset, we share it with no license but with the statement that for these data, there are no legal restrictions, and these can be re-used by a third party for any lawful activity.

2. If there are copyright-protected works present in a particular dataset, we share it under the license Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC BY 4.0) to waive as many of rights as possible.
3. If there are *sui generis* database-protected works present in particular dataset, we share it under the license Creative Commons Zero (CC0) to waive as many of rights as possible.
4. If there are personal data, we apply best practices of anonymization and pseudoanonymization of data and where it is possible, we share it under one of the conditions 1–3 above. Otherwise, pseudonymized data are kept in a managed regime and they are provided upon an individual research request which will go through standard scientific and ethical assessment (protocol of the study, informed consent, data protection assurance etc.).
5. If there are any 3. party rights (copyright, personal data etc.) we evaluate each of these datasets from the legal point of view based on our 'standard practise' and proceed in accordance with these particular conditions.

In future DMP versions, there will be a more precise description of each dataset that we consider important for our research center also from the legal point of view. These formulations of what we consider best legal practise in our field of research will be used for development/modification of international standards.

7 Ethical Aspects

All data, including biological materials, are processed in accordance with European Union – Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons concerning the processing of personal data and the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR). Data processing is also in compliance with national legislation: Personal Data Processing Act (Act No. 110/2019 Coll.) and the Health Services Act (Act No. 372/2011 Coll., as amended).